

Microwave induced synthesis, spectral characterization and antimicrobial studies of copper(II) complexes containing mixed ligands, Schiff bases and 1,10-phenanthroline

Smita S. Giri, Shrimant V. Rathod* and Sandip D. Maind

Chemistry Research Laboratory, Department of Chemistry,
Bharatiya Vidya Bhavan's Hazarimal Somani College of Arts and Science, Kulapati K. M. Munshi Marg,
Chowpatty, Mumbai-400 007, India

E-mail : shrees.rathod@gmail.com

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Abstract : Copper(II) complexes containing mixed ligands, Schiff bases ($L_1 = (2\text{-carboxyphenyl})\text{-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine}$ and $L_2 = 5\text{-NO}_2\text{-(2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine}$) and 1,10-phenanthroline has been synthesized by conventional and microwave methods. These copper(II) complexes have been characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductance, magnetic moment, IR, UV-Visible spectra and thermal analysis. The copper(II) complexes are green and brownish green colored and stable in air. On the basis of these spectral studies, it is revealed that all the complexes exhibited 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) ratio with the coordination number 6. Thermal data show degradation pattern of the complexes. The thermal behavior of metal complexes shows that the hydrated complexes loses water molecules of hydration in the first step; followed by decomposition of ligand molecules in the subsequent steps. The Schiff base ligands and its copper(II) complexes have been tested for their antimicrobial behavior against various microorganisms. The antimicrobial analysis revealed that copper(II) complex prepared by Schiff base ($L_2 = 5\text{-NO}_2\text{-(2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine}$) and 1,10-phenanthroline is more active than copper(II) complex prepared by Schiff base ($L_1 = (2\text{-carboxyphenyl})\text{-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine}$) and 1,10-phenanthroline.

Keywords : Microwave synthesis, spectral characterization, mixed ligands, Schiff bases, copper(II) complexes, antimicrobial studies.

Introduction

In 21st century the whole world is looking surprisingly towards coordination chemistry as the frontier of chemistry due to its architecturally designed Schiff base complexes and fascinating advances in structural, spectral, non-linear optics, photochemical, electrochemical, biochemical properties. A large number of Schiff bases and their metal complexes have been studied because their interesting characteristics in the field of material science and biological systems. Optoelectronic, electrical and magnetic properties of the metals and metalloids can be tailored by reacting them with different ligands. Schiff bases and their complexes may exhibit the properties like to reversibly bind oxygen, transfer of an amino group, as nanoprecursors and varied complexing/redox ability. The Schiff bases have high affinity to chelate with the transition metal ions, hence are attracting attention due to po-

tential applications in various fields¹⁻⁴. Schiff base ligands containing O and N donor atoms play an important role in coordination chemistry related to catalysis and enzymatic reaction, magnetism and molecular architecture. In metal complexes, on chelation the polarity of the metal ion will be reduced to a greater extent due to the overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with donor groups. Further, it increases the delocalization of π -electrons over the whole chelate ring. Metal complexes with novel Schiff base ligands are reported by various authors^{5,6}.

Metal complexes of 1,10-phenanthroline and its derivatives are of increasing interest because of their versatile role in chemistry⁷. The mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) with phen, 2-methyl lactate was reported which play an important role in biological process⁸. The complexes containing mixed ligands, Schiff bases, and 1,10-

phenanthroline have good microbial activities compared to the ligands and have significant potential as antimicrobial agents. The large ring size of 1,10-phenanthroline moiety makes the complexes more lipophilic. This increased lipophilicity enhances the penetration of the metal complexes into lipid membranes and block the metal binding sites in the enzymes. The azomethine linkage and hetero aromatic moiety in the synthesized complexes exhibit extensive biological activities^{9,10}.

Microwave induced synthesis is a branch of green chemistry. The application of microwave-assisted synthesis in organic, organometallic and coordination chemistry continues to develop at an astonishing space. The salient features of microwave approach are shorter reaction time, simple reaction conditions and enhancement in yields¹¹⁻¹³. Reports on the synthesis of metal complexes by microwave methods have been comparatively less. Microwave reactions under solvent free or less solvent conditions are attractive offering reduced pollution, low cost and offer high yields together with simplicity in processing and handling.

In this study, we report the synthesis, physicochemical characterization and biological significances of Cu^{II} complexes containing mixed ligands, Schiff bases, (L₁ = (2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine and L₂ = 5-NO₂-(2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine) (Fig. 1) and 1,10-phenanthroline. The reaction was carried out by both conventional and microwave methods. The metal complexes formed with these two new ligands can be used as precursors for the synthesis of new compounds which exhibit interesting physical, chemical and biological properties.

Experimental

Materials :

2-Acetyl-pyridine, 2-aminobenzoic acid, 2-amino-5-nitrobenzoic acid, CuCl₂.2H₂O, ethanol, DMSO and DMF was procured from S.D. fine chem. 1,10-Phenanthroline procured from Merck.

Conventional method for synthesis of Schiff base ligands (L₁/L₂) :

The Schiff base ligands (2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine (L₁) and 5-NO₂-(2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine (L₂) were synthesized by mixing a solution of 2-acetyl-pyridine (0.121 g, 1 mmol) in 10 ml of ethanol with solution of 2-aminobenzoic acid (0.137 g, 1 mmol)/2-amino-5-nitrobenzoic acid (0.285 g, 1 mmol) with constant stirring. The resulting mixture was refluxed at 60 °C until the completion of reaction (checked by TLC). The resultant brown colored liquid was concentrated and kept for air evaporation. The shiny brown needle crystalline product was obtained, washed with ether and dried. The reactions were completed in 2 h with yields (72% (L₁) and 78% (L₂)).

Microwave method for synthesis of Schiff base ligands (L₁/L₂) :

The Schiff base ligands (2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine (L₁) and 5-NO₂-(2-carboxyphenyl)-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine (L₂) were synthesized by mixing of a solution 2-acetyl-pyridine (0.121 g, 1 mmol) in 10 ml of ethanol with solution of 2-aminobenzoic acid (0.137 g, 1 mmol)/2-amino-5-nitrobenzoic acid (0.285 g, 1 mmol) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was then irradiated by the microwave oven. The resulting

Fig. 1. Synthesis and structure of the ligands (L₁ and L₂).

product was then recrystallized with ethanol and finally dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a desiccator. The progress of the reaction and purity of the product was monitored by TLC. The reactions were completed in 6 min with yields (81% (L_1) and 88% (L_2)).

Conventional method for synthesis of $[\text{CuL}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ ($L = L_1/L_2$) :

To a ethanolic solution of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.170 g, 1 mmol), a ethanolic solution of L_1/L_2 (0.240 g; 1 mmol/0.285 g; 1 mmol) was added followed by the addition of 1,10-phenanthroline (0.181 g; 1 mmol) as secondary ligand with constant stirring. Resulting solution was refluxed at 60 °C until the completion of reaction (checked by TLC). The resulting solid green product was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over CaCl_2 . It was further dried in electric oven at 50 °C to 70 °C. The reactions were completed in 2 h with yields (67% ($[\text{CuL}_1(\text{phen})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$) and 71% ($[\text{CuL}_2(\text{phen})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$)).

Microwave method for synthesis of $[\text{CuL}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ ($L = L_1/L_2$) :

To a ethanolic solution of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.170 g, 1 mmol), a ethanolic solution of L_1/L_2 (0.240 g; 1 mmol/0.285 g; 1 mmol) was added followed by the addition of 1,10-phenanthroline (0.181 g; 1 mmol) as secondary ligand with constant stirring. Resulting solution was irradiated by the microwave oven. The resulting product was then recrystallized with ethanol and finally dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous CaCl_2 in a desiccator. The progress of the reaction and purity of the product was monitored by TLC. The reactions were completed in 6 min with yields (81% $[\text{CuL}_1(\text{phen})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$) and 84% ($[\text{CuL}_2(\text{phen})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$)).

Methods :

Microwave assisted synthesis were carried out in open glass vessel on a modified microwave oven model 2001 ETB with rotating tray and a power source 230 V, microwave energy output 800 W and microwave frequency 2450 MHz. A thermocouple device was used to monitor the temperature inside the vessel of the microwave. The microwave reactions were performed using on/off cycling to control the temperature. Copper was analyzed by titrimetric method. Elemental analysis (C, H and N) were performed on a Thermo Finnigan FLASH EA-112 CHNS analyzer. Molar conductance (Λ_M) was measured on the

ELICO (CM-185) conductivity bridge using *ca.* 10^{-3} M solution in DMF. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on Gouy balance at room temperature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer IR spectrometer as KBr pellets in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} spectral range. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer using DMSO as a solvent. UV-Visible spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-Visible NIR spectrophotometer equipped with quartz cuvette of 1 cm^3 path length at room temperature. Thermal analysis (TG and DTA) measurements of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer thermal analyzer, under nitrogen atmosphere with a heating rate of 10 °C min^{-1} in the temperature range R.T. – 1000 °C.

Antimicrobial analysis :

The *in vitro* antibacterial activity of the investigated Schiff base and their metal complexes was screened against the bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by disc diffusion method using nutrient agar as medium and Streptomycin as control. The antifungal activities of the Schiff base and their metal complexes were tested by the well diffusion method against the fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Candida albicans*, on potato dextrose agar as the medium and Miconazole as control. Each of the compounds was dissolved in DMSO and solutions of different concentrations (25, 50 and 100 ppm) were prepared separately. In a typical procedure, a well was made on agar medium inoculated with microorganism. The well was filled with the test solution using a micropipette and the plate was incubated 24 h for bacteria at 37 °C and 72 h for fungi at 30 °C. During this period, the test solution diffused and the growth of the inoculated microorganism was affected. The inhibition zone was developed, at which the concentration was noted. All determinations were performed in thrice.

Results and discussion

The microwave induced synthesis was observed that the reaction was completed in a short time with higher yields compared to the conventional method. In the microwave method homogeneity of reaction mixture was increased by the rotating of reaction platform tray. The metal complexes are coloured, crystalline solid, non-hygroscopic and stable towards air and moisture at room temperature. They decompose on heating at high tem-

perature, soluble in DMF, DMSO and less soluble in common organic solvents. All the metal chelates have 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. They were obtained with excellent yield because of the intramolecular hydrogen bond between the fairly acidic phenolic hydrogen and the azomethine nitrogen atom in 2-acetyl-pyridine or its derivatives, which catalyzes the condensation reactions. The coordination of the Cu metal of the tridentate (ONN) ligands is realized by means of pyridine nitrogen atom and azomethine of the ligands and one oxygen of the ligands. The reaction of 2-acetyl-pyridine with 2-amino-benzoic acid/2-amino-5-nitrobenzoic acid readily forms the ligands L₁/L₂ which is easily identified by IR and ¹H NMR spectra. The two Schiff bases could coordinate to the metal atoms through the phenolate oxygen, imine nitrogen, and amine nitrogen atoms. The copper(II) complexes adopt octahedral geometry by following synthesis procedure.

Elemental analysis :

Experimental values of Cu in complexes and C, H and N in ligands and complexes is given in Table 1. It is observed that the experimental values of Cu was close

agreement with calculated value. The elemental analyses show 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

Molar conductance :

The metal complexes were dissolved in DMF and the molar conductivities of 10⁻³ M of their solutions at room temperature were measured to establish the charge of the metal complexes. The molar conductance values shown in Table 1 which indicate that, the metal complexes having conductivity values in the range characteristic of the non-electrolytic nature suggesting that these complexes are neutral¹⁴.

Magnetic moment :

Magnetic moments of the metal complexes are listed in Table 1. The octahedral geometry of copper(II) ion in all complexes is confirmed by the measured magnetic moment values in the range 1.74–1.75 μ_B which is in harmony with the reported value.

IR spectra :

IR spectral data of ligands and complexes is given in Table 2. Typical IR spectra of ligands L₁ and L₂ is shown in Fig. 2. The IR spectra of Schiff base ligands L₁ and L₂ show bands at 1669–1677 cm⁻¹, may be assigned to the νC=O (carboxylic group)¹⁵⁻¹⁷. However, the spectra of

Table 1. Analytical and physico-chemical data of the ligands and copper(II) complexes

Ligands and copper(II) complexes (Colour)	Mol. formula	Mol. wt.	M.p. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Λ _M (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff}
				Cu	C	H	N		
L ₁ (Golden brown)	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂	240.25	148	–	69.98 (69.98)	4.99 (5.03)	11.66 (11.66)	–	–
[CuL ₁ (phen)Cl]Cl (Green)	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₂ Cl ₂ Cu	553.99	> 300	10.28 (11.46)	55.55 (56.36)	3.10 (3.45)	9.10 (10.11)	52.58	1.74
L ₂ (Orange brown)	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	285.25	162	–	58.95 (58.94)	3.85 (3.88)	14.73 (14.73)	–	–
[CuL ₂ (phen)Cl]Cl (Green)	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Cl ₂ Cu	563.49	> 300	11.04 (11.27)	54.29 (55.41)	3.32 (3.21)	11.04 (12.43)	49.40	1.75

Table 2. Infrared spectral data of the ligands and copper(II) complexes

Ligands and copper(II) complexes	νC=N	COO ⁻	1,10-Phenanthroline	Py-N
L ₁	1617	1672	–	659
[CuL ₁ (phen)Cl]Cl	1614	1591, 1325	1538, 1409, 869, 717	644
L ₂	1631	1677	–	591
[CuL ₂ (phen)Cl]Cl	1626	1542, 1384	1542, 1428, 845, 721	574

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. IR spectra of (a) L_1 and (b) L_2 .

all complexes show absence of this band accompanied by the appearance of two characteristic bands at $1625\text{--}1605\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1409\text{--}1374\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to asymmetric and symmetrical stretching of the carboxylic group respectively, indicating the involvement of the carboxylic oxygen atom in the complex formation. The mode of coordination of carboxylate group has often been deduced from the magnitude of the observed separation between the $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-)$. The separation value (Δ) between $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-)$ in metal complexes was more than

200 cm^{-1} ($270\text{--}205\text{ cm}^{-1}$) suggests the coordination of carboxylate group in all metal complexes in a monodentate fashion. The azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ ¹⁸ bands in the IR spectra of the ligands appear in the range $1610\text{--}1635\text{ cm}^{-1}$, shifting of this band¹⁹ towards the lower frequency region by $15\text{--}25\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes indicates involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination with metal ion. The pyridine ring deformation mode at $\sim 620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these spectra of the free ligands is shifted to higher wave numbers in the spectra of the complexes indicating coor-

dination of the complexes indicating coordination of the pyridine ring nitrogen atom to the copper(II)²⁰. The 1,10-phenanthroline bands at 722 cm⁻¹ shows their involvement in the complexes.

NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR spectra of ligands L₁ and L₂ are shown in Fig. 3. The ¹H NMR data of ligands L₁ and L₂ is as follows : L₁ - δ 2.48 ppm (s, H₃C-C=N); δ 6.5–8.3 ppm (m < ArH); δ 8.5 ppm (s, -C=N), L₂ - δ 2.3 ppm (s,

H₃C-C=N); δ 6.5–8.3 ppm (m < ArH); δ 8.4 ppm (s, -C=N).

UV-Visible spectra :

UV-Visible spectral data of ligands and complexes is given in Table 3. The complexes show essentially three sets of common bands, falling in the range 270 nm to 780 nm. The very intense bands at lower wavelength have been assigned to charge transfer transition, for complexes with aromatic bridges these bands occur at longer wave-

Fig. 3. ¹H NMR spectra of (a) L₁ and (b) L₂.

Table 3. UV-Visible spectral data of the ligands and copper(II) complexes

Ligands and copper(II) complexes	$\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions and charge transfer transitions (nm)	$d \rightarrow d$ transitions (nm)
L ₁	252, 275, 345	-
[CuL ₁ (phen)Cl]Cl	250, 275	650, 730
L ₂	276, 332, 410	-
[CuL ₂ (phen)Cl]Cl	260, 275, 410	650, 725

length, as expected from the higher aromaticity of the ligands which eases delocalization of electron density. On the other hand, the observed new shoulder around 410 nm in the spectra of the complexes solutions can be likely ascribed to an intermolecular transition from the ligands molecules to the vacant orbitals localized on the coordinated metal ions. The weaker band in the region 520 nm to 780 nm in the spectra of complexes with aliphatic imines is assigned to unresolved transitions from the lower empty d_{xy} orbital which proposes octahedral geometry²¹ for complexes, which is contradictory by the literature which showed that, it could not be observed for complexes with aromatic imines bridges since it is masked by the high charge transfer transitions²².

Thermal analysis :

The thermal decomposition studies of copper(II) complexes of L₁ and L₂ were carried in the temperature range of 20 to 1200 °C. The typical TG, DTG and DTA curve of [CuL₁(phen)Cl]Cl is shown in Fig. 4. The complex

[CuL₁(phen)Cl]Cl undergoes decomposition in three steps. There is no mass loss up to 190 °C revealing the absence of either water or solvent molecules in this complex. The first stage takes place in the 170 °C to 270 °C range with DTG peak at 230 °C corresponding to mass loss 6.36% may be attributed to the decomposition of chlorine molecule (calculated mass loss = 6.84%). The second stage takes place in 270 °C to 440 °C range corresponding to mass loss 34 to 96% may be attributed to the decomposition of 1,10-phenantroline molecule (calculated mass loss = 34.74%) with one broad DTG peak at 380 to 1195 °C with weak endothermic peak 980 °C corresponding to the decomposition of Schiff base leaving anhydrous CuO, 14.6% and calculated loss 15.3% molecule in which the DTA endothermic peaks at 660 °C and 1025 °C with weak multiplets at 960 °C and 990 °C²³. Similar type of decomposition pattern was observed for the complex [CuL₂(phen)Cl]Cl. Thermal analysis confirmed the stability of the complex.

Fig. 4. Typical TG, DTG and DTA curve of [CuL₁(phen)Cl]Cl.

Antimicrobial analysis :

The bactericidal and fungicidal investigation data of Schiff base ligands and their corresponding metal complexes are summarized in Tables 4 and 5. The synthesized Schiff base ligands and their corresponding metal complexes were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against bacteria *E. coli* and *S. aureus* and *in vitro* antifungal activity against two fungi *A. niger* and *C. albicans*. All of the tested compounds showed good biological activity against microorganism. Moreover, all the complexes are moderately active as compared to the standard bactericide and fungicide (Streptomycin and Miconazole). A comparative study of the ligands and their copper(II) complexes indicates that the complexes are more active than their respective ligands. The activity increases

upon coordination. The increased activity of the metal chelates than those of the ligands can be explained on the basis of Overtone's concept and Chelation theory. On chelation, the polarity of the metal ion will be reduced to a greater extent due to the overlap of the ligand orbital and partial sharing of the positive charge of the metal ion with donor groups²⁴. Further, it increases the delocalization of the π -electrons over the whole chelating ring and enhances the penetration of the complexes into lipid membranes and blocking of the metal binding sites in the enzymes of microorganisms. There are other factors also, which increase the activity of the complexes²⁵ viz. stability constant, solubility, molar conductance, magnetic moment, lipophilicity and hydrophilicity, M-L bond length etc.

Table 4. Antibacterial screening of ligands and copper(II) complexes

Ligands and copper(II) complexes	<i>E. coli</i>						<i>S. aureus</i>					
	Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)			Activity index (%) ^b			Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)			Activity index (%) ^b		
	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a
L ₁	14	15	16	66	65	57	10	13	15	55	56	60
[CuL ₁ (phen)Cl]Cl	18	22	25	85	95	89	18	20	24	100	86	96
L ₂	15	13	19	71	56	67	10	12	12	55	52	48
[CuL ₂ (phen)Cl]Cl	20	23	27	95	100	96	18	22	24	100	95	96
Streptomycin (Control)	21	23	28	100	100	100	18	23	25	100	100	100

^aConcentration in ppm.

$${}^b\text{Activity index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Zone of inhibition by test compound (diameter)}}{\text{Zone of inhibition by test standard (diameter)}} \times 100$$

Table 5. Antifungal screening of ligands and copper(II) complexes

Ligands and copper(II) complexes	<i>A. niger</i>						<i>C. albicans</i>					
	Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)			Activity index (%) ^b			Diameter of inhibition zone (in mm)			Activity index (%) ^b		
	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a	25 ^a	50 ^a	100 ^a
L ₁	13	14	20	59	56	66	16	16	18	66	66	64
[CuL ₁ (phen)Cl]Cl	19	23	27	86	92	90	18	21	23	75	87	82
L ₂	13	15	21	59	60	70	14	19	18	58	79	64
[CuL ₂ (phen)Cl]Cl	20	23	27	90	92	90	20	23	28	83	95	100
Miconazole (Control)	22	25	30	100	100	100	24	24	28	100	100	100

^aConcentration in ppm.

$${}^b\text{Activity index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Zone of inhibition by test compound (diameter)}}{\text{Zone of inhibition by test standard (diameter)}} \times 100$$

Conclusion

In case of microwave assisted synthesis, it was observed that the reaction time decreased from hours to minutes and availability of the product with better yield as compared to the conventional method. Solvent use was minimized is advantageous in the present work. The coordination chemistry of the Schiff base ligands ($L_1 = (2\text{-carboxyphenyl})\text{-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine}$; $L_2 = 5\text{-NO}_2\text{-}(2\text{-carboxyphenyl})\text{-pyridine-2-ylethyleneamine}$) and their copper(II) complexes with Cl^- and 1,10-phenanthroline as secondary ligand were described and characterized on the basis of analytical, magnetic, spectra data as well as thermal analysis. The Schiff bases ligands act as monobasic tridentate, coordinated to the metal ions in a tridentate manner with ONN donor sites of the carbonyl oxygen, azomethine nitrogen, and pyridine nitrogen along with anion and two nitrogen of 1,10-phenanthroline in the complex formation and in ligands, the coordination mode of carboxylate group is unidentate mode, correlating the experimental data, one can suggest the octahedral geometry for the prepared metal complexes. The Cu^{II} complexes shows high intensity fluorescence with high quantum yield in DMF solvent than the corresponding ligands. The antimicrobial data showed that the metal complexes to be more biologically active compared to those parent Schiff base ligands against all pathogenic species. Such studies may assist to search some novel chemotherapeutics to answer the emerging problem of drug resistance in health sciences.

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